

Structural investigation of Mt. Merapi by an active seismic experiment

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Abstract

At Merapi volcano, central Java, an active seismic experiment was carried out in the years 1997 and 1998 as a contribution to the German-Indonesian joint project MERAPI. Using deterministic wide-angle refraction and stochastic methods, the seismic structure was investigated along three profiles until approximately 300 m depth. The seismic source was a mudgun operated in three artificial water basins located on the flanks of the volcano at altitudes of about 1000 m. Shots were recorded along seismometer lines arranged radially with respect to the summit and consisting of up to 30 three-component seismometers each (100 m spacing). The standard data processing included trace editing, stacking of up to 100 single shots, and in some cases the application of f-k filters to separate back and forth travelling waves. To analyse vector properties of the wave field, the covariance matrix of the three-component data is calculated and various measures of rectilinearity and particle motion are determined. These analyses lead to the design of a polarisation filter that enhanced the first break and later onsets with a mostly vertical particle motion in the otherwise structureless wave field behind the first break. Arrival times of first and later onsets were modelled by two-dimensional ray tracing in a layered 1-D model with P-velocities of some hundred m/s near the surface and more than 3000 m/s at a maximum depth of about 300 m. Later onsets in the seismograms are interpreted as refracted waves reflected at steeply-dipping fracture zones. The most prominent fracture zones observed on the southern and western volcano flanks are located at the same distances (~ 2 km, ~ 3.5 km) to the summit of Mt. Merapi and may belong to a larger, approximately circular weakness zone.

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At Merapi volcano, central Java, an active seismic experiment was realised in the years 1997 and 1998 as a contribution to the German-Indonesian joint project MERAPI. Using deterministic wide-angle refraction and stochastic methods, the seismic structure was investigated along three profiles until approximately 300 m depth.

Shots were fired at three seismic source points located in Trono (western slope), Bebung (south), and Batur (north-east) in an altitude of about 1000 m. Each source was equipped with a 2.5 l mudgun operated in an artificial water basin at pressures of 8 to 10 MPa. The high repetition accuracy of this kind of source enables stacking of single shots to improve the signal-to-noise ratio and also the combination of data recorded at different time or location to one seismogram (Wegler et al., 1999). The seismic signals of each basin were recorded along up to four seismometer lines (BAB, BEB, BIB and SEL), which were arranged radially with respect to the summit and consisted of up to 30 1 Hz three-component seismometers each (cf. Figure 4). This acquisition geometry was mostly enforced by the topography.

The standard data processing included trace editing, stacking of up to 100 single shots, bandpass filtering, and in some cases the application of f-k filters to separate back and forth travelling waves (Lühr et al., 1998). Figure 1 shows the vertical component of line BEB, bandpass filtered on the left, and the negative wavenumber portion on the right. After a sharp but with increasing offset rapidly weakening first break, a complicated wave field develops, including high amplitude coda waves. These are typical for any seismogram recorded at Mt. Merapi. But besides that, many linear onsets are apparent in the f-k filtered section. Those originating at the first break are interpreted as refractions reflected at steeply dipping reflectors, while others may be backscattered surface waves, some of them offline. Scattering and absorption processes cause the remaining incoherence, especially of the coda waves, which is discussed by Wegler et al. (2000). The observed linear, coherent phases contain information on larger scale structures below the seismic lines. To enhance these type of waves all three components are jointly processed by means of a polarisation analysis.

To analyse vector properties of the wave field the covariance matrix of the three-component data is calculated within a moving time window. Evaluating eigenvalues of the covariance matrix and their corresponding eigenvectors, various measures of rectilinearity and the direction of particle motion are determined. The analysis of all near source profiles with an offset of up to 4 km yields a high degree of linear polarisation for the first arrivals, whereas the strong coda waves show diffuse results. For all these profiles the horizontal azimuth of the main direction of polarisation is very variable, which may be due to scattering processes. Furthermore the energy of coda waves is mainly on the horizontal components. However, a few later onsets can be detected with dominant vertical polarisation.

This leads to the design of a polarisation filter to emphasise later onsets with a mostly vertical particle motion in the otherwise structureless wave field behind the first break. The filter used here considers the main direction of polarisation and a measure of rectilinearity (Kanasewich, 1981; Maercklin, 1999). Weighting exponents and a smoothing operator are applied to both parameters. The filtered vertical component of line BEB shows a strong first break and enhanced reflected refractions (Figure 2). This is also true for line BAB, and even on a line with an offset of roughly 7.5 km first break times become pickable. Line BIB appears to be free from reflections of that type.

A two-dimensional ray tracing supports the interpretation of first and later onsets (Figure 3). The model is based on a layered 1-D depth profile of the P-velocity derived from first break travel times. The velocities range from some hundred m/s close to the surface to more than 3000 m/s at a maximum depth of approximately 300 m. Each layer consists of different geological horizons

and only an effective velocity is defined. deviations from subparallel bedding cannot be modelled reasonably at the moment. With reflectors perpendicular to these layers it is possible to fit travel time curves of selected onsets. The model shown in Figure 3 (bottom) assumes a P-to-S-wave conversion at reflector A, 3 km from the source, to explain the lower apparent velocity of the reflected onsets A and B (Figure 3, top).

The impedance contrasts at both modelled reflectors must be very high because of the high amplitudes of the reflected waves. This can be explained with deeply penetrating fracture zones at these locations. With this explanation these fracture or weakness zones are mapped on Mt. Merapi using observed reflections on lines BEB and BAB (Figure 4). The most prominent fracture zones on both profiles are equidistant to the summit of Mt. Merapi and may belong to a larger, approximately circular weakness zone.

In conclusion, active seismics as implemented here provides velocity and structure information along the flanks down to about 300 m below the surface. To image seismic velocities in greater depth a longer profile across the volcano edifice is suggested, which may utilise explosive sources.

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Figure 1: Trace-normalised vertical component of shot record BEB. After stacking 82 single shots the data are filtered using a bandpass only (left) and a f-k filter for the negative wavenumber portion of the wave field (right). Solid lines mark the trend of the first break.

Figure 2: Vertical component of the shot record BEB. The data are processed with a zero-phase bandpass and the described polarisation filter. here a 2 s AGC is applied for display.

Figure 3: Modelled ray paths and travel time curves for selected onsets on line BEB. The model is based on a simple 1-D velocity-depth function and reflectors perpendicular to the layers. Letters A and B denote reflectors and corresponding time curves, black boxes measured travel times. The depth is in m below the surface.

Figure 4: Location of seismic lines, source points, and mapped fracture zones. Profiles shown as dotted lines were not interpreted. Two circles mark the extend of possible weakness zones.